

Childhood Trauma and its Predictive Influence On Fear Of Happiness And Suicidal Ideation Among Adult

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Abstract

Childhood trauma is a widely recognized well-established risk factor for later psychological distress, yet its influence on beliefs about happiness and suicidal ideation remains less understood in South Asian contexts. This study examined the predictive role childhood trauma plays in fear of happiness and suicidal ideation among 470 Pakistani adults aged 19–35. Standardized instruments, including the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire-Short Form (CTQ-SF), Fear of Happiness Scale, and Suicidal Ideation Attributes Scale (SIDAS), were administered. Results showed that childhood trauma did not significantly predict fear of happiness and it appeared to be shaped more by cultural belief systems than past trauma. However, childhood trauma strongly predicted suicidal ideation, and fear of happiness was positively associated with suicidal thoughts. The results have suggested that while cultural narratives may drive fear of happiness, unresolved childhood trauma remains a key predictor of suicidal vulnerability. Culturally sensitive, trauma-informed interventions are crucial to addressing these intertwined risk factors.

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INTRODUCTION

Childhood Trauma

Trauma can be defined as a distinguished experience that results in triggering the feelings of fear, helplessness, or fright and endangers injury, death, or honor. Traumatic events, by definition, are such events that include violence, abuse, neglect, accidents, loss, war, disasters, and different emotionally disruptive happenings (APA, 2000). Childhood Trauma is described as being exposed to either real or threatened injuries, death, or sexual abuse and violence. These events include being exposed to direct trauma, witness any traumatic event, or getting to know about trauma faced by any friend or family (Bellis & Zisk, 2014).

It has been indicated by different studies that individuals with Childhood Traumas are likely to develop learning problems, physical health problems like diabetes and heart disease, psychiatric issues like aggression, depression, emotional distress, PTSD and psychotic disorders, suicidal tendency and idea, low esteem, indulging in high-risk behaviors, loss of pleasure, difficulty of solving problems and decision-making. It has also been proven by researches that childhood trauma is a risk factor in elevating suicidal behavior and depression in adulthood (Zarse et al., 2019).

According to the WHO surveys, over a third of the population has gone through childhood adversity. A study done on German population revealed that 2.6 percent, 3.3 percent, and 2.3 percent of participants' experienced emotional, physical, and sexual abuse respectively, as 7 percent and 9 percent experienced emotional and physical neglect during their childhood life. In United States 66 and 152 men and women out of 1442 participants responded that they had experience Childhood Trauma (Briere & Elliott, 2003). Out of 478 respondents, 130 men and 101 women were treated as victims of physical and emotional child abuse in Pakistan (Sadia et al., 2019).

Childhood trauma is linked to the on sight of various problems as discussed above. The main focus of this study is on two variables; Fear of Happiness and Suicidal Ideation.

Fear of Happiness

Fear of Happiness is defined as a belief system where people consider that being happy would result in negative results. Hence, they avoid happiness in different circumstances. It is also believed that happiness is an internal state and one could whether control or achieve it. In conservative communities, people possess superstitious belief that expressing happiness can result in harm and negative consequences. They believe that it may also result in being confronted by evil eye, rivalry, or negative consequences in after-life. Maintaining such belief system may result in risking mental health (Tekke & Özer, 2019).

Researches have shown that Fear of Happiness results in declined psychological well-being, lessened positive effects and heightened positive effects. It is also linked with decreased life satisfaction, less self-esteem, resilience, loss of hope and decreased health factors such as loss of sleep and isolation (Lambert et al., 2022). It is a risk factor for increased levels of OCD, depression, anxiety, phobias, anxiety, interpersonal sensitivity, paranoid thinking. It also increases the risk of different behavioral issues such as anti-social behavior, issues in academic performance. It is more prevalent among eastern cultures. It is more likely for East Asians to think that happiness may result in something bad. Because East Asian culture is influenced by Taoism, according to which it is suggested that everything eventually will revert to its opposite. This belief is present but to a lesser degree in western cultures (Tekke & Ceylan, 2021).

Suicidal Ideation

Suicidal thoughts or ideation means when people start thinking about committing suicide. These thoughts can lead from just a simple consideration to the detailed planning of committing suicide. It is when a person wants to take their own life and they keep on thinking about suicide (Brazier, 2018).

A person who might be experiencing any kind of suicidal thoughts might have the symptoms like feelings of being trapped and hopelessness, cannot tolerate emotional pain, have any abnormal preoccupation with violence, dying and even death, experiencing a lot of mood swings, talk mostly about taking revenge or have guilt, engage in risky behavior like driving carelessly, giving many of their own things away and lack of concentration. However, a lot of people who have Suicidal Ideation keep their thoughts a secret and avoid talking about such thoughts. (Purse, 2020)

There are several risk factors of suicide, such as suicidal attempt done before in life, feelings of being worthless, likes staying alone or lonely, experiencing any traumatic event in life, have a substance abuse problem or disorder, facing any psychiatric disorder like depression, PTSD or bipolar disorder, having a family history of mental disorders and unsupportive family or a hostile environment (Brazier, 2018).

According to researches, in the general population, the suicidal ideation is present globally between 3.1% - 56% (Nock et al., 2008). This paper also showed that the estimated lifetime prevalence of suicidal ideation in the cross-national sample involving 100 percent is 9.2 percent. In the US, prevalence of SI in Colombia was found to be 33.2%, while in Mexico 39%. In Europe, prevalence of suicidal ideation was recorded 32.2% in Belgium, 35.9% in France and 22.1 % in Germany. The pervasiveness of suicidal ideation was 21%, and the model effectively anticipated connections among the constructs and chance of Suicidal Ideation and endeavors (Yang L et al., 2019).

Researches have shown strong correlation between childhood trauma and suicidal ideation. A study by Bahk et al., (2016) considered the relationship between the two variables. 211 healthy adults were taken as a sample for this purpose. Path analysis was used. It proved that childhood maltreatment and trauma directly predict suicidal ideation.

In conclusion the current study will foresee childhood trauma and its predictive influence on fear of happiness and suicidal ideation among adult.

Objectives

1. To measure the predictive relationship between Childhood Trauma, Fear of Happiness and Suicidal Ideation among adult population.
2. To identify the relationship between Childhood Trauma, Fear of Happiness and Suicidal Ideation.
3. To study the DV (Fear of Happiness, Suicidal Ideation) among adults in relation to their demographic determinants.

Need and Significance of Study

Childhood Trauma has resulted in the creation of global health crisis. People are being affected by it all around the world. Not only their physical health but mental health is also at risk due to it. Fear of Happiness is also prevalent in different cultures including Pakistan. Different researches have focused on cultural influence on Fear of Happiness but not different other important factors like Childhood Trauma. Moreover, Suicidal Ideation is another phenomenon becoming quite common among youth and adult population. The current study will help explore the relation between these variables. It will allow us to

understand if Childhood Trauma is the predictor of Fear of Happiness and Suicidal Ideation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The main goal of the present study is to recognize whether or not childhood trauma is a trauma predictor of fear of happiness and suicidal thoughts in adults within Pakistan.

A research study by Kwan et al., (2021) tried to explain how childhood abuse influences the subjective happiness and the contribution of the emotion intelligence as mediating factor. The research has been carried out on adolescent population in Hong Kong, China. This type of survey was cross sectional and the sampling done on nine secondary schools. It used the sample of 1694 individuals. The scale of Child Abuse and Trauma, scale of The Wong and Law Emotional competence and scale of Subjective Happiness were employed. The results of the study showed that a significant impact was present between child abuse and subjective happiness.

Early-life trauma and mishandled treatments has a long-lasting effect on mature life. Research spearheaded by Volgenau, (2023) examined the interconnection between the two (childhood maltreatment and wellbeing). To this end, two studies were undertaken. In study 1, network was applied so as to discover the association between the two variables. In contrast to study 2, where an additional sample of adults was gained in order to obtain a confirmatory test on the network obtained in study 1. The findings indicated that childhood abuse has an influence of thriving in adulthood. It results in the loss of personal well-being and eventually lessens volumes of happiness.

This study was conducted to find out how negative experiences in childhood and psychosocial resource have influence on the well-being of an individual. To this end, a cross-sectional study was implemented in two different institutes of mental health/addiction treatment facilities. A total sample of 176 was realized. Demographic data was obtained and SCID-DSM-IV, CHQ and other scales were administered. Subsequently, the collected data was run using a regression analysis and correlation analysis. The findings of the research indicated that childhood adversities such as physical abuse or death of parents were associated with a decreased well-being and happiness of its subjects (Elroy & Hevey, 2014).

In a descriptive study, the mediating role of alexithymia and fear of happiness in the correlation between psychological well-being and trauma was determined (Soleimani, 2019). Based on the analysis, the fictitious model $RMSEA=0.55$, $CFI=0.92$, $X^2/df=2.588$ fit in the measurement model. The results of the analysis showed that fear and alexithymia had mediating influences in childhood trauma (Torabi, 2019).

Childhood trauma is regarded among some of the major variables that causes the prediction of the suicidal ideation. Bahk et al., (2017) also undertook a study to establish the correlation between childhood trauma and suicidal thoughts. A sample comprising of 211 participants was selected and various tests conducted which involved Childhood Trauma Questionnaire and Beck Scale of Self-destructive Ideation. Path analysis was utilized to measure the relationship between the respective variables. The findings of the research indicated that childhood maltreatment is directly defining the presence of suicidal ideation amongst the individuals in question.

Another research attempted to establish the relationships with suicidal ideas. The research studied the connection that exists between childhood trauma and suicidal thoughts with a discovery of the effect brought about by depressive symptoms and the sense of guidelines that are in trouble. To this end, a student sample of 372 drawn out of

various colleges was considered. The participants filled the self-report questionnaires addressing the experiences of childhood trauma, ability to perceive rules, suicidal ideations, and any other depressive symptoms. In the present report, the confirmatory factor analysis was adopted. The findings of the given study were that childhood trauma and suicidal ideas are interconnected with each other. There can be a lower risk of suicidal ideation and finally suicide that can be developed with the aid of better interventions. With the knowledge of these process variations, the algorithm will be implemented (Laghaei et al., n.a.).

Epidemiological studies have suggested traumatic childhood as a risk factor to the suicidal ideation. To advance on the understanding of further issues of this problem, Berardelli et al., (2022) functioned path analytic model to understand how the different forms of maltreatment in childhood may affect suicidal ideation and whether there are hopelessness and dissociative symptoms mediation the implementation of which. The research population consisted of 215 adult inpatients at the psychiatric unit of the Sant Andrea Medical Center, in Rome, Italy. In an attempt to test the hypotheses, the Beck Hopelessness Scale, Columbia-Suicide Severity Rating Scale, Dissociative Experiences Scale-II, and Childhood Trauma Questionnaire were used. Results showed that sexual abuse have had a direct impact on suicide ideation $\beta = 0.18$ $SE = 0.8$, $p < 0.05$, with emotional abuse and neglect being negative predictors of suicidal ideation in all analyses, specifically, by increasing suicidal ideation through an indirect effect on dissociation ($\beta = 0.05$, $SE = 0.02$, $95\%CI 0.01/0.09$), and on hopelessness ($\beta = 0.10$).

METHODOLOGY

The study aims to find out if Childhood Trauma is a strong predictor of Fear of Happiness and Suicidal Ideation among adults in Pakistan.

Target Population

Data was collected from adults living in Gujrat and Jalalpur Jattan (Pakistan).

Research Design

The current study was conducted to explore Childhood Trauma as the predictor of Fear of Happiness and Suicidal Ideation. For this purpose, cross-sectional research design was used.

Sampling Technique

Due to shortage of time, convenient sampling technique was adopted to collect data from targeted population.

Sample Size

A sample size of 470 participants was taken in order to conduct the research.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Both genders, male and female were included in the study.
2. Individuals with English language understanding was included.
3. Adults with age range of 19-35 were included.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Individuals with physical and psychological disabilities were excluded.
2. Adults with age above 35 were excluded from the study.

Instruments

Consent form

Before conduction of the test, individuals were provided with the consent form and their consent was taken. Participants were informed about the objectives, method and purpose of study.

Demographics Form

The demographic variables included name, age, religion, socioeconomic status, gender, education, city, area, marital status and family system (nuclear/joint).

Childhood Trauma Questionnaire-Short Form (CTQ-SF)

Childhood Trauma Questionnaire is a well-known instrument to manage childhood ill-treatment in the adult population. The scale is an abridged version of a 70-item Childhood Trauma Questionnaire (Bernstein et al., 1994) adopted by Bernstein et al., in 2003. The number of items in the TQ-SF is 28 in which 25 items are intended to measure childhood trauma. These 25 items also are composed of 5 subscales. It consists of subscales namely Emotional Abuse, Sexual Abuse, Physical Abuse, Emotional Neglect and Physical Neglect. The other 3 questions evaluate Minimization/ Denial. Questions on the scale are responded to on a 5-point Likert scale. Respondents are meant to respond to items which are coded as never true, rarely, a few times, often and very often. Each of the items of CTQ-SF starts with the indication of the growing up period.

Fear of Happiness

Fear of Happiness scale was designed in 2012 by Gilbert. The scale uses 9 items with the rating that lies on a 5- Likert scale. The respondents score independently each of the items with the choices varying between the ranges of 0 (Not at all like me) to 4 (Extremely like me). The scale is developed to measure the anxiousness of people and their perception about the feeling of positive and happiness. The statements in the scale were established in the course of therapy sessions conducted with author PG (e.g., I do not deserve to be happy). More than that, Gilbert and team rated each item in terms of face validity. It is a valid and reliable scale due to Cronbach's alpha value .90.

Suicidal Ideation Attributes Scale (SIDAS)

The scale was created by Spijker et al., (2014) to screen individuals if any suicidal thoughts are present among people in the community. It is a five-item scale and each item is targeting one characteristic regarding suicidal ideation. The responses to the scale are measured on a 10-point scale. A higher total score is meant to reflect severity in suicidal thoughts. The scale has high internal consistency (Cronbach alpha= 0.91). It measures the factors like frequency, level of distress and closeness to attempt are associated with suicidal thoughts and its effect on daily functioning.

Procedure

In the study, a sample of 470 participants was collected using the cross-sectional research design and convenient sampling technique. Data was aimed to be collected from Gujrat and Jalalpur Jattan in Pakistan. Adults were targeted with the age range of 19-35 years. Data was collected by approaching the participants physically and by creating Google form.

Before getting the questionnaires filled, the participants were given all the instructions and purpose of the study was explained. The informed consent was taken and participants were assured that their provided data would remain confidential. After successfully establishing the rapport, participants were given the demographics form that included age, socioeconomic status, religion, gender, education, city, area, marital status and family system (nuclear/joint). Later on, the required questionnaires including Childhood Trauma Questionnaire (CTQ-FS), Fear of Happiness, and Suicidal Ideation Attributes Scale (SIDAS) were applied in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are providing the detailed description of statistical analysis employed in the research. Whereas this section of research provides the statistical view of the relationship

among variables. All the statistical analysis was done by statistical package for social sciences. (SPSS, V 24.0)

Data Screening

Data screening is done to ensure the integrity of the data we entered on the SPSS. Because it is very important to screen the data for the variables and cases used for the analysis in the report. Because the data screening means to check the errors in the data and also fixing and removing the errors in the report or in the data.

Demographic information was collected from the sample that is reported in table 4.1 given below.

Table 4.1: Demographic characteristics (N= 470)

Variables	F	%
Age		
19-22	318	67.7
23-26	108	23
27-30	25	5.4
31-35	14	3
Gender		
Men	96	20.4
Women	374	79.6
Education		
Matriculation	3	0.6
Intermediate	55	11.7
Undergraduate	391	83.2
Postgraduate	21	4.5
Area		
Urban	266	56.6
Rural	204	43.4
Marital status		
Unmarried	419	89.1
Married	46	9.8

Divorced	5	1.1
Family system		
Joint	222	47.2
Nuclear	248	52.8

Table 4.1 shows the frequencies and percentage of sample’s demographic determinants. These characteristics include age, gender, education, area, marital status, and family system. The age of majority of the members lied in 26-30 (i.e., 44.5%). The age of majority of the participants was 21 (i.e., 19.8%) whereas only 0.2% lied in the age range of 35. Out of the whole sample, female participants were higher (79.6%) as compared to male participants i.e., 20.4%. Out of the 470 participants, the majority of them belonged to urban areas (i.e., 56.6%) and 43.4% belonged to rural areas. However, the difference between the two is not very significant. Marital status of the majority population was single that makes 89.1% of the sample. Only 9.8% were married and 1.1% were divorced. 52.8% of the sample belonged to the nuclear family system and 47.2% belonged to the joint family system. There is less difference between the two categories in the respective sample.

Table 4.2: Summary of correlation (N=470)

Variables	1	2	3
Childhood trauma	—	.03	.18**
Fear of happiness		—	.29**
Suicidal ideation			—

The table shows the correlation between childhood trauma and fear of happiness. The value .03 that is showing no significant correlation between the two variables. Further, the result shows weak positive correlation between childhood trauma and suicidal ideation. Finally, the correlation between fear of happiness and suicidal ideation results show positive correlation i.e., .286. It means increase fear of happiness leads to increase suicidal ideation.

Table 4.5: Summary of regression (N=470)

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	P
Childhood Trauma	.025	.001	-.002	.293	.588
Fear of Happiness					

Table 4.5 shows the summary of regression analysis. The study explored that Childhood Trauma is not the significant predictor of Fear of Happiness in the respective sample. Most of the research shows that Fear of Happiness is linked with cultural faith and belief systems. Some studies also showed that fear of happiness is linked to how social orders see articulation of joy. This might be the reason why Childhood Trauma is not predicting Fear of Happiness in our population. (Joshnloo et al., 2014; Phillip, 2023; Saini et al., 2022)

Table 4.6: Summary of Regression Analysis of Childhood Trauma and Fear of Happiness

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	P
	B	SE	Beta		
Constant	17.025	1.445	.025	11.785	.000
Fear of Happiness	0.13	.023		.542	.000

The values of standard linear regression have indicated that childhood trauma is not a good predictor of fear of happiness (B=.013, p=.000).

Table 4.7: Summary of Regression (N=470)

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	P
Childhood Trauma Suicidal Ideation	.180	.032	.030	15.620	.000

The Table 4.7 represents the summary of a regression analysis of childhood trauma and suicidal ideation. Linear regression showed that childhood trauma is a dominant feature that predicts suicidal ideation. The significant p-value of childhood trauma was able to explain this as the child trauma being the predictor of suicidal thought.

Table 4.8: Summary of Regression Analysis of Childhood Trauma and Suicidal Ideation

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	P
	B	SE	Beta		
Constant	6.461	1.563	.180	4.133	.000
Suicidal Ideation	.099	.025		3.952	.000

The findings suggest that childhood trauma is the major predictor of suicidal ideas. Consequently, it is clear that higher the childhood trauma, the higher suicidal ideation among the respondents (B=.099, p=.000).

Table 4.9: Summary of Regression (N=470)

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	P
Fear of Happiness Suicidal Ideation	.286	.082	.030	41.763	.000

Table 4.9 shows the summary of regression analysis of fear of happiness and suicidal ideation. The results show that fear of happiness is the predictor of suicidal ideation. The results show that R=.286 which means that both the variables are positively correlated i.e., increased childhood trauma increases the chances of suicidal ideation.

Table 4.10: Summary of Regression Analysis of Fear of Happiness and Suicidal Ideation

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized coefficients		
	B	SE	Beta	t	P
Constant	6.881	.932	.286	7.381	.000
Fear of Happiness	.315	.049		6.462	.000

The results of standard linear regression analysis show that fear of happiness and suicidal ideation are strongly predicting each other (B=.315, p=.000).

DISCUSSION

The result of the study showed that child abuse and child abuse are not associated with fear of happiness. Calculated, however, it indicates a significant relationship existing between childhood trauma and suicidal thoughts. There was a 32 percent variability in suicidal ideation with alterations in childhood trauma. There was a lack of an explicit relationship between traumas experienced during childhood and the fear of happiness. The outcomes were displayed to demonstrate 1 percent variance in fear of happiness instigated as a result of childhood trauma.

Childhood trauma and its drastic effects on mental health have been a topic of numerous researches. Research studies have tried to capture the complex relationships between childhood trauma, fear of happiness and suicidal ideation. The results of the research produced an idea that childhood trauma does not directly relate to the aspect of fear of happiness, but it has a significant association with suicidal ideation. The link between childhood trauma and suicidal thoughts has been something that has been researched to have the following impacts. Some studies indicated that fear of happiness may be determined by cultural beliefs and norms put in place by society. Fear of happiness can be quite a cultural and societal issue of how people in different societies and cultures see happiness when it is achieved and expressed. Fear of happiness seems to be independent of sex or history of childhood trauma as well as perceived stress is, in this sample. Apprehensions of euphoria may have a lot to do with the perceptions, towards the achievement and expression of joy, as compared to that of suffering, or anxiety. It is strongly recommended that we hold prejudices when it comes to universalization and equality to gender and sex (Saini et al., 2021).

The earlier study also concurred with the present study in the sense that there exists a positive relationship between childhood trauma and suicidal ideation. Since I used the findings of a study (Zarrati et al., 2019) that was cited to establish the mediation power of mental pain in the interconnection between childhood trauma and suicidal ideation, mental pain is a potential mediator of the relationship between childhood trauma and suicidal ideation. The comparison of research hypothetic model in terms of the fitness indices showed that the hypothetic model fits with the model of measurement (CFI = 0.96, NFI = 0.95, SRMR = 0.062). The results have shown both the direct and indirect influence of childhood trauma on suicide ideation.

CONCLUSION

The study was aimed at investigating the relationship between childhood trauma, fear of happiness and suicidal ideations. The design of the study was that of cross-sectional because it was aimed at attaining the research objectives. The study incorporated three of

these variables in such a way that one was the independent variable, which was childhood trauma and two were the dependent variables; fear of happiness and suicide ideation. The findings showed that childhood trauma was not pertinent to fear of happiness, but the significant predictor of suicidal ideation.

Overall, the present research opens new dimensions for the further research. The restraint of the current research is that the data was collected using the English versions of the questionnaires. In future, it is recommended to use Urdu version to get more reliable results. Furthermore, the study was conducted on a specific age group of adult population (19-35). Future researches should also include adolescents and other parts of the population in the researches as well when studying similar variables.

REFERENCES

- Ahi, Q., Tavasoli, A., Pahlevan, A., & Mansouri, A. (2021). The mediating role of cognitive emotion regulation in the relationship between childhood trauma and fear of happiness. *Zahedan Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*.
- American Psychiatric Association. (2000). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (4th ed., Text rev.). Washington, DC: Author.
- Bahk, Y. C., Jang, S. K., Choi, K. H., & Lee, S. H. (2017). The relationship between childhood trauma and suicidal ideation: Role of maltreatment and potential mediators. *Psychiatry Investigation*, 14(1), 37-43. <https://doi.org/10.4306/pi.2017.14.1.37>
- Berardelli, I., Sarubbi, S., Rogante, E., Erbutto, D., Giuliani, C., Lamis, D. A., Innamorati, M., & Pompili, M. (2022). Association between childhood maltreatment and suicidal ideation: A path analysis study. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 11(8), 2179. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm11082179>
- Bernstein, D. P., Stein, J. A., Newcomb, M. D., Walker, E., Pogge, D., Ahluvalia, T., ... & Zule, W. (2003). Development and validation of a brief screening version of the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 27(2), 169-190. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0145-2134\(02\)00506-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0145-2134(02)00506-6)
- Brazier, Y. (2018). What are suicidal thoughts? *Medical News Today*. <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/193026>
- Briere, J., & Elliott, D. M. (2003). Prevalence and psychological sequelae of self-reported childhood physical and sexual abuse in a general population sample of men and women. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 27(10), 1205-1222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2003.09.008>
- De Bellis, M. D., & Zisk, A. (2014). The biological effects of childhood trauma. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatric Clinics of North America*, 23(2), 185-222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chc.2014.01.002>
- De Mattos Souza, L. D., Molina, M. L., Da Silva, R. A., & Jansen, K. (2016). History of childhood trauma as risk factors to suicide risk in major depression. *Psychiatry Research*, 246, 612-616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2016.11.002>
- Enoch, M. A. (2011). The role of early life stress as a predictor for alcohol and drug dependence. *Psychopharmacology*, 214(1), 17-31. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-010-1916-6>
- Gilbert, P., McEwan, K., Gibbons, L., Chotai, S., Duarte, J., & Matos, M. (2012). Fears of compassion and happiness in relation to alexithymia, mindfulness, and self-criticism. *Psychology and Psychotherapy: Theory, Research and Practice*, 85(4), 374-390. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8341.2011.02046.x>

- Hagborg, J. M., Kalin, T., & Gerdner, A. (2022). The Childhood Trauma Questionnaire-Short Form (CTQ-SF) used with adolescents: Methodological report from clinical and community samples. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Trauma*, 15(4), 1199–1213. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40653-022-00443-8>
- Kwan, C. K., & Kwok, S. Y. (2021). The impact of childhood emotional abuse on adolescents' subjective happiness: The mediating role of emotional intelligence. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 16, 2387–2401. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11482-021-09916-8>
- Laghaei, M., Mehrabizadeh Honarmand, M., Jobson, L., et al. (2023). Pathways from childhood trauma to suicidal ideation: Mediating through difficulties in emotion regulation and depressive symptoms. *BMC Psychiatry*, 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-023-05265-w>
- Lambert, L., Draper, Z. A., Warren, M. A., et al. (2022). Conceptions of happiness matter: Relationships between fear and fragility of happiness and mental and physical wellbeing. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 23, 535–560. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-021-00413-1>
- McElroy, S., & Hevey, D. (2014). Relationship between adverse early experiences, stressors, psychosocial resources and wellbeing. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 38(1), 65–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2013.07.017>
- Mustafa Tekke, & Özer, B. (2019). Fear of happiness: Religious and psychological implications in Turkey. *Mental Health, Religion & Culture*, 22(7), 686–693. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13674676.2019.1625314>
- Nock, M. K., Green, J. G., Hwang, I., McLaughlin, K. A., Sampson, N. A., Zaslavsky, A. M., et al. (2013). Prevalence, correlates, and treatment of lifetime suicidal behavior among adolescents: Results from the National Comorbidity Survey Replication Adolescent Supplement. *JAMA Psychiatry*, 70(3), 300–310. <https://doi.org/10.1001/2013.jamapsychiatry.55>
- Purse, M. (2020). What is suicidal ideation? *Verywell Mind*. <https://www.verywellmind.com/suicidal-ideation-380609>
- Sadia, M., et al. (2019). Gender comparisons and prevalence of child abuse and post-traumatic stress disorder symptoms in adolescents. *Journal of the Pakistan Medical Association*.
- Saini, M., Jha, M., Warikoo, S., & Jha, K. (2021). Fear of happiness and its correlates with gender, adverse childhood experiences and perceived stress among medical graduate students in India. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 9(3). <https://doi.org/10.25215/0903.022>
- Şar, V., Türk, T., & Öztürk, E. (2019). Fear of happiness among college students: The role of gender, childhood psychological trauma, and dissociation. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, 61(4), 389–394. https://doi.org/10.4103/psychiatry.IndianJPsychiatry_52_17
- Soleimani, A., Lashkari, A., & Torabi, Y. (2019). The relationship between trauma and psychological well-being: The mediating role of fear of happiness and alexithymia. *Journal of Psychological Studies*.
- Tekke, M., & Ceylan, D. (2021). Exploring the link between fear of happiness, separation anxiety and religious coping of adolescents in Turkey. *International Journal of Eurasia Social Sciences*.

- Van Spijker, B. A. J., Batterham, P. J., Calear, A. L., Farrer, L., Christensen, H., Reynolds, J., & Kerkhof, A. J. F. M. (2014). The Suicidal Ideation Attributes Scale (SIDAS): Community-based validation study of a new scale for the measurement of suicidal ideation. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 44(4), 408–419. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sltb.12084>
- Volgenau, K. M., Hokes, K. E., Hacker, N., et al. (2023). A network analysis approach to understanding the relationship between childhood trauma and wellbeing later in life. *Child Psychiatry & Human Development*, 54, 1127–1140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10578-022-01321-y>
- Yang, L., Liu, X., Chen, W., & Li, L. (2019). A test of the three-step theory of suicide among Chinese people: A study based on the ideation-to-action framework. *Archives of Suicide Research*, 23(4), 648–661. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1381118.2018.1494659>
- Yildirim, M., & Aziz, I. A. (2017). Psychometric properties of Turkish form of the fear of happiness scale. *The Journal of Happiness & Well-Being*, 5(2), 187–195.
- Yildirim, M., Barmanpek, U., & Farag, A. A. (2018). Reliability and validity studies of externality of happiness scale among Turkish adults. *European Scientific Journal*, 14(14), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2018.v14n14p1>
- Zarrati, I., Bermas, H., & Sabet, M. (2019). The relationship between childhood trauma and suicide ideation: Mediating role of mental pain. *Annals of Military and Health Sciences Research*, 17(3). <https://doi.org/10.5812/amh.94877>
- Zarse, E., Neff, M., Yoder, R., Hulvershorn, L., Chambers, J., & Chambers, R. (2019). The adverse childhood experiences questionnaire: Two decades of research on childhood trauma as a primary cause of adult mental illness, addiction, and medical diseases. *Cogent Medicine*, 6(1), 1581447. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331205X.2019.1581447>